

Strategic Incentive Design in The Durable Consumer Goods Industry – A Case Study

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Abstract

This case examines how a mid-sized European manufacturer faces interrelated management-accounting challenges as it diversifies from a mature, low-complexity product line into a technologically advanced premium segment. The shift in product complexity exposes weaknesses in traditional costing, internal transfer prices, and salesforce incentive structures. The case demonstrates how volume-based absorption costing can mask idle capacity and distort product costs, while a Time-Driven Activity-Based Costing approach yields more accurate insights for operational and pricing decisions. It further shows how transfer prices must incorporate opportunity costs when capacity is constrained, in order to prevent systematic goal incongruence between decentralized units. Finally, the case illustrates how narrowly designed performance targets and cash-only bonus contracts can bias sales behavior toward short-term, low-effort products and undermine strategic priorities. The analysis provides a cohesive platform for studying costing systems, transfer-pricing mechanisms, and incentive design in a changing product environment.

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1 Introduction

The company: Nordic AquaTek A/S was founded in 1998 in Odense, Denmark. The company began as a small manufacturer of outdoor hot tubs made of thermo-wood. Over the following years it expanded into a mid-sized European supplier of premium water-leisure products. The firm now employs approximately 280 people across manufacturing, design, sales, and after-service. It sells throughout Scandinavia, Germany, the Benelux region, and Northern France. Product portfolio: The company operates two major product lines.

Hot Tubs. These products are heated water basins for private gardens and holiday homes. They include a simple wooden or fiberglass shell, an electrical heating element, and basic controls. Assembly is straightforward. Customization is limited to size, color, and insulation level. Nordic AquaTek views this segment as its stable cash generator. Volumes are predictable and margins have historically been acceptable.

Whirlpools. The second product line includes premium spas with multi-jet massage systems, integrated pumps, and digital control units. These models require substantially more assembly time and a greater number of components. Customers expect high performance, exact quality control, and extensive after-sales support. The segment has grown rapidly due to rising demand in high-income households and small hotels. Management believes that this line has significant strategic potential.

Operational Structure: Production takes place in a single facility that contains three main operating departments: Shell Fabrication Department (SFD); Components & Assembly Department (CAD); Sales & Service Department (SSD). All employees record their hours in a traditional time-keeping system. Overheads are allocated using a volume-based rate derived from total direct labor hours. The accounting department refers to this as a 'simple and robust' absorption costing system. However, engineers in the Assembly department have repeatedly expressed concerns that the system does not reflect actual resource consumption, particularly for the more complex whirlpool models.

Competitive pressure: Nordic AquaTek faces increasing competition. Low-cost producers from Eastern Europe have entered the basic hot tub market with aggressive pricing. At the

same time, high-end whirlpool manufacturers from Germany and the United States promote technologically advanced systems. Management fears that the existing costing approach may misrepresent the profitability of the two product lines. Initial internal analyses suggest that the premium spas may be far more resource-intensive than previously assumed, and that the current product margins may be misleading.

Internal Tensions: The introduction of the whirlpool line required new investments, including specialized pumps and electronic components. The engineering department argues that it needs more autonomy to source components and redesign production flows. The finance function demands strict adherence to annual budgets. These conflicting expectations create friction, especially in meetings where performance metrics and bonus targets are discussed.

Current decision point: The CFO Winnie Spaaning has asked the management accounting team to prepare a revised profitability analysis. The goal is to understand how resources are actually consumed across the two product lines, and whether transfer-pricing arrangements and incentive schemes support the firm's strategic priorities. The team considers implementing Time-Driven Activity-Based Costing in one department as a pilot. At the same time, the CFO questions whether the current transfer pricing approach for internal components distorts decisions. Finally, Winnie has suggested revisiting the incentive system, since early observations indicate that the current bonus system reinforces short-term, individualistic behavior in SSD, discourages the promotion of whirlpools, and fails to support the collaborative and long-term customer development efforts required for the new product line.

2 Time-Driven Activity-based Costing

Nordic AquaTek A/S relies on competitive tenders for its hot tub and whirlpool sales. For the coming quarter, the company expects to produce 200 hot tubs and 80 whirlpools. Precise costing is essential for winning these tenders. Management believes that the current volume-based absorption costing system misrepresents resource consumption in the Assembly and Testing Department, especially for the more complex whirlpools that require extensive installation of pumps, jets, electronic modules, and wiring. The company therefore contrasts

the existing costing system with a newly developed Time-Driven Activity-Based Costing (TDABC) approach. This comparison aims to improve the accuracy of product costing and support informed bidding decisions.

In the *current* absorption costing system, all direct costs (materials, assembly labor) are traced directly. The *direct* manufacturing labor rate is DKK 350 per hour. The Assembly and Testing Department applies a single overhead rate based on direct labor hours (see Table 1 for the necessary data).

For the new TDABC pilot, the Assembly and Testing Department has identified three core activities with their practical capacity levels and associated costs (Table 1). The time equations for the two product groups reflect observed production requirements and are considered reliable.

Hot tub = Assembly: 1.0 hours + Testing: 1.5 hours + Quality assurance: 0.5 hours

Whirlpool = Assembly: 4.0 hours + Testing: 3.5 hours + Quality assurance: 1.5 hours

Table 1: Overhead cost and activity structure and cost pools (per quarter)

Activity cost pool	Time measure (hours)	Budgeted hours (hours)	Total overhead cost (DKK)
Assembly support	Assembly hours	700	1,750,000
Testing and calibration	Testing hours	650	1,202,500
Quality assurance	QA hours	300	1,005,000
Total	—	1,650	3,957,500

Direct materials are estimated at 15,500 DKK per hot tub and 23,000 DKK per whirlpool.

Direct labor is estimated at 13 hours per hot tub and 15 hours per whirlpool.

Required

- 1) Calculate the full cost of a hot tub and a whirlpool using the current absorption costing system.
- 2) Calculate the full cost of a hot tub and a whirlpool using the TDABC pilot.
- 3) To the surprise of the production manager, now both(!) products show lower overhead costs under TDABC than under the absorption-costing system. Explain the difference numerically, using the activity rates and capacities provided.

3 Transfer Pricing

Nordic AquaTek's operative Components & Assembly Department (CAD) produces standard assembly units for its hot tubs.

- CAD incurs variable manufacturing costs of 20,050 DKK per hot tub, and charges a transfer price of 34,000 DKK to the Sales & Service Department (SSD), as both departments are evaluated as profit centers.
- CAD incurs variable manufacturing costs of 28,250 DKK per whirlpool. So far, Nordic AquaTek does not have a transfer price for whirlpools.

On average, SSD invoices customers 50,000 DKK for one finished hot tub, and 75,000 DKK for a whirlpool. SSD's selling expenses amount to 2,000 DKK per unit for either product. When CAD does not produce hot tubs, they will use their full capacity of 3,900 hours per quarter to produce whirlpools instead. The processing time for one hot tub assembly is 13 hours. The processing time for one whirlpool assembly is 15 hours. Different from the hot tubs, CAD incurs a small, additional external certification cost of 653.85 DKK for every whirlpool sold.

Required

- 4) Calculate the current profit of CAD and SSD, respectively, for one hot tub.
- 5) Explain numerically which range of transfer prices is feasible for a hot tub if only hot tubs were produced.
- 6) CAD operates at full capacity, so whirlpools replace hot tubs when produced. Determine the transfer price per whirlpool (in DKK) that makes CAD economically indifferent between producing hot tubs (see transfer price above) and whirlpools for SSD.
- 7) An accounting-illiterate manager mocks the management accountants: "*No one understands what you mean by this 'indifference' calculation. Let me tell you how I would manage it: we ask CAD what the real, true costs are that they can prove with invoices, and that is our transfer price, problem solved!*" Briefly explain to this person—without calculations—why (a) opportunity cost must be considered in transfer pricing when capacity is limited, and (b) which type of highly dysfunctional behavior their idea would cause among the managers of CAD.

4 Incentive systems

Todd Hubb is the head of sales at SSD, and although he has always enjoyed selling hot tubs, he has recently voiced concerns to CFO Winnie Spaaning about the way Nordic AquaTek structures incentives for selling whirlpools. The current system is simple: each salesperson receives a fixed percentage of the contribution margin of every product they sell. The only goal that matters is the financial contribution generated within the quarter, and the only form of payment is a cash bonus. This structure worked reasonably well when the product portfolio was stable and demand was predictable, but Todd now observes that it shapes behavior in ways that run counter to Nordic AquaTek's strategic ambition to expand the whirlpool segment.

Todd says: "I see two major issues. The first one is that our salespeople's behavior in selling the whirlpools is not aligned with what our strategy aims for. The targets we set for SSD push them toward short-term revenue and contribution margin, but they do not reflect how different these two product lines actually are. Selling a whirlpool is far more demanding: customers need extensive information upfront, installation takes more coordination, service expectations are higher, and any early malfunction immediately returns as an operational burden for my team. Yet our targets treat whirlpools and hot tubs as if they required the same effort, the same risk, and the same customer relationship work. As a result, no one in SSD is eager to pursue the premium segment—even though the company claims it is our future. We do not measure product mix, we do not track whether we are reaching strategic customer groups, we do not look at satisfaction after installation, and we do not credit salespeople for developing long-term customer potential. Everyone focuses only on hitting quarterly numbers, not on building up the market for whirlpools. Our targets send the wrong message, and the message is: choose the easy sale, avoid the difficult one, and forget about the strategic priorities."

Todd continues: "The second issue is that my staff lacks the motivation to act as a team. They lack the motivation to go the extra mile, and I believe this is largely due to how we design the bonus contracts. The current system pays out only on individual quarterly results, which means every salesperson works in isolation. There is no reason to share customer leads, no reason to help a colleague with a complex whirlpool case, no reason to

think beyond this quarter. The tighter the bonus budget, the more internal gaming and territorial behavior I see—people withholding information, protecting ‘their’ accounts, and avoiding anything that might slow down their personal numbers. The contract rewards quick wins, not the long-term development of our premium segment, and it certainly does not reward collaboration. With limited cash available for bonuses, we need smarter, more creative payout structures—ones that motivate effort on the difficult sales, support the introduction of whirlpools, strengthen team spirit, and make people proud to contribute to SSD’s broader goals rather than just their own short-term scorecard.”

Required

- 8) The CFO believes that the current performance targets used in SSD create suboptimal behavior among sales people. Provide two concrete suggestions for how SSD’s target-setting system should be better aligned with the corporate strategy.
- 9) The CFO also concludes that the current bonus contract does not reward the behaviors Nordic AquaTek needs. Propose four improvements to the bonus plan structure, focusing on what should be rewarded and how payouts should be structured.

5 Discussion of the case

The following suggestions for solutions are presented in the same numbering as the requirements. They are intended as possible directions for class discussion or examination rather than definitive answers. They build on insights from similar case analyses and studies in the field, as cited in the reference list, and should be adapted to the specific teaching environment and learning objectives of each course or workshop.

-- A suggested solution is available from the author upon request. --

References

- Atkinson, A. A., Kaplan, R. S., Matsumura, E. M., & Young, S. M. (2022). *Management Accounting, International Edition* (7th ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge Business Publishers.
- Chong, V. K. (1996). Management Accounting Systems, Task Uncertainty and Managerial Performance: A Research Note. *Accounting, Organizations and Society, 21*(5), 415–421.
- Dalci, I., Tanis, V., & Kosan, L. (2010). Customer profitability analysis with time-driven activity-based costing: a case study in a hotel. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management, 22*(5), 609–637.
- Datar, S. M., & Rajan, M. V. (2020). *Hornngren's Cost Accounting: A Managerial Emphasis*. Harlow: Pearson.
- Dearman, D. T., & Shields, M. D. (2001). Cost Knowledge and Cost-Based Judgment Performance. *Journal of Management Accounting Research, 13*, 1–18.
- Glazer, R., Steckel, J. H., & Winer, R. S. (1992). Locally rational decision making: The distracting effect of information on managerial performance. *Management Science, 38*(2), 212–226.
- Govindarajan, V., & Gupta, A. K. (1985). Linking Control System to Business Unit Strategy: Impact on Performance. *Accounting, Organizations and Society, 10*(1), 51–66.
- Grabski, S. V. (1996). Transfer pricing in complex organizations: A review and integration of recent empirical and analytical research. *Readings in accounting for management control*, 453–495.
- Ittner, C. D., Larcker, D. F., & Rajan, M. V. (1997). The Choice of Performance Measures in Annual Bonus Contracts. *Accounting Review, 72*(2), 231–255.
- Kaplan, R. S., & Anderson, S. R. (2004). Time-driven Activity-based Costing. *Harvard Business Review, 82*(11), 131–138.
- Lambert, D. R. (1979). Transfer pricing and interdivisional conflict. *California Management Review, 21*(4), 70–75.
- Lovata, L. M., & Costigan, M. L. (2002). Empirical analysis of adopters of Economic Value Added. *Management Accounting Research, 13*(2), 215–228.
- Lueg, R. (2015). Customer accounting with budgets and activity-based costing: a case study in retail banking. *Journal of Academy of Business and Economics, 15*(2), 41–48.
- Lueg, R. (2015). Product customization: A case study on choosing the right costing system. *International Journal of Business Strategy, 15*(2), 63–68.
- Lueg, R. (2019). Internet of things and process performance improvements in manufacturing. *International Journal of Business Research, 19*(2), 63–72.
- Lueg, R. (2019). Strategy execution in higher education. *International Journal of Business Strategy, 19*(1), 57–63.
- Lueg, R. (2019). Transfer prices and compensation: an Activity-based Costing approach in the telecommunications industry. *European Journal of Management, 19*(2), 27–34.
- Lueg, R. (2020). Activity-based costing as a basis for transfer prices and target setting. *International Journal of Economics & Business Administration, 8*(3), 489–499.
- Lueg, R. (2020). Balanced Scorecard implementations – The case of a city hall. *European Journal of Management, 20*(1), 41–48.
- Lueg, R. (2020). Customer accounting and free return policies of retailers. *International Journal of Business Research, 20*(1), 89–94.
- Lueg, R. (2020). Strategy execution in hospitals. *Journal of International Business and Economics, 20*(1), 25–32.
- Lueg, R. (2021). New product development and flawed cause-and-effect relations in strategy maps. *European Journal of Management, 21*(1), 58–65.
- Lueg, R. (2021). Segment profitability in the leisure industry. *International Journal of Business Strategy, 21*(1), 25–34.
- Lueg, R. (2021). Subjectivity and fairness in bonus plans. *International Journal of Strategic Management, 21*(1), 48–56.
- Lueg, R. (2022). Lagged effects in the Balanced Scorecard. *Journal of International Business and Economics, 20*(4), 25–32.
- Lueg, R. (2022). Motivational effects of management control systems in assisted living facilities. *Journal of Academy of Business and Economics, 22*(2), 20–39.
- Lueg, R. (2022). Opportunity cost and incentive systems. *European Journal of Management, 22*(1), 49–58.

- Lueg, R. (2022). Quality and time-related indicators in incentive plans. *Journal of International Business and Economics*, 22(1), forthcoming.
- Lueg, R. (2022). The Sustainability Balanced Scorecard and venture capital ownership. *International Journal of Business Research*, 22(1), 25–33.
- Lueg, R. (2022). Target setting for operational performance improvements. *International Journal of Strategic Management*, 22(1), 31–38.
- Lueg, R. (2024). Cost of quality reports and value engineering. *European Journal of Management*, 24(2), 79–88.
- Lueg, R. (2024). Performance incentives in activity-based management. *International Journal of Business Research*, 24(1), 62–69.
- Lueg, R. (2024). Strategic cost management in new drug development. *International Journal of Business Research*, 24(2), 14–23.
- Lueg, R. (2025). The alignment of compensation plans with transfer prices. *European Journal of Management*, 25(2), 5–13.
- Lueg, R. (2025). Balancing cost, quality, and strategy: A case in performance management. *European Journal of Management*, 25(3), forthcoming.
- Lueg, R. (2025). Balancing incentives and ethics. *European Journal of Management*, 25(1), 48–57.
- Lueg, R. (2025). Beyond product margins: The shift to customer profitability. *International Journal of Business Research*, 25(2), 28–37.
- Lueg, R. (2025). From costing to performance management: how Time-Driven Activity-based Costing enhances employee accountability. *Journal of Academy of Business and Economics*, 25(4), forthcoming.
- Lueg, R. (2025). Leveraging theory of constraints and Activity-based Costing for improved manufacturing performance. *International Journal of Business Research*, 25(3), forthcoming.
- Lueg, R. (2025). Optimizing operational efficiency: A Balanced Scorecard approach in the circular economy. *Journal of Academy of Business and Economics*, 25(3), forthcoming.
- Lueg, R. (2025). Strategic profitability analysis and incentive alignment. *Journal of Academy of Business and Economics*, 25(1), 180–193.
- Lueg, R. (2025). Translating strategic market analysis to internal value creation. *International Journal of Business Research*, 24(1), 35–41.
- Lueg, R., & Lueg, K. (2013). The Balanced Scorecard and different Business Models in the textile industry - A case study. *International Journal of Strategic Management*, 13(2), 61–66.
- Onsi, M. (1970). A transfer pricing system based on opportunity cost. *The Accounting Review*, 45(3), 535–543.
- Pashkevich, N., von Schéele, F., & Haftor, D. M. (2023). Accounting for cognitive time in activity-based costing: A technology for the management of digital economy. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 186, 122176.
- Pernot, E., Roodhooft, F., & Van den Abbeele, A. (2007). Time-driven activity-based costing for inter-library services: a case study in a university. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 33(5), 551–560.
- Schuster, P., & Clarke, P. (2010). Transfer Prices: Functions, Types, and Behavioral Implications. *Management accounting quarterly*, 11(2).
- Talwar, A. K. (1974). "Transfer Pricing System Based on Opportunity Costs": A Comment. *The Accounting Review*, 49(1), 126–128.
- van Raaij, E. M. (2005). The strategic value of customer profitability analysis. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 23(4), 372–381.
- Young, G., Beckman, H., & Baker, E. (2012). Financial incentives, professional values and performance: a study of pay-for-performance in a professional organization. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 33(7), 964–983.